

COPING BEHAVIOR IN STRESSFUL SITUATIONS IN ADOLESCENTS SOCIAL AND PSYCHOLOGICAL STRATEGIES OF MANIFESTATION FEATURES

Nosirova Sitorabonu Alisher qizi

Osiyo Xalqaro Universiteti magistrati

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Abstract: In this article, protection of adolescents in extreme situations mechanisms, coping was carried out in the field of behavioral manifestations in scientific observation based on the data collected on the basis of research held, mainly the psychological views of foreign psychologists in this regard the relationship between them is analyzed, a research method for studying the problem based on the results, a conclusion is given.

Key words: coping behavior, coping strategy, coping, protection mechanism, "two factor" theory, "coping behavior

The problem of coping behavior is always the most pressing one facing humanity has been one of the problems. After all, the social development of a person in all aspects, activity and self-development as a person largely depends on this process depends

.In psychology, coping behavior emerged in the second half of the 20th century. Copy behavior is taken from the English language "cope, to cope" - to overcome, overcome means. This term was first used by L. Murphy in 1962 in children used when learning how to overcome a problem during a crisis.

And A. Maslau introduced this term to science. Coping behavior in general characterized by the individual's readiness to solve life problems. He has the ability to use the means to overcome problems manifests, which is characterized by the elimination of stressful behavior.

R. S. Lazarus, one of the leading experts who researched coping styles According to his opinion, there are two global types of coping strategies: (elimination of stress method) - aim at the problem, take a subjective aim.

The problem-oriented type is oriented towards a rational solution to a difficult situation and help from others to independently analyze the situation in their behavior there is a tendency to seek information from additional sources is the type.

The subjective goal-setting type is an emotional solution to the situation in overcoming stress they do, they have an absolute desire to do a specific job, to think about a problem have no desires, they express their sorrows through negative emotional means they compensate by alcohol, sleep, and food. They are their own they use passive strategies more intensively in restoring their

emotional balance, if a person has no knowledge of the situation or his real capabilities stressor pressure decreases if he cannot use it.

It is known that the concept of "overcoming life problems" itself is different becomes important. First of all, this is a constantly changing process. Wills T. and Shifman S. believes that this process can be divided into three stages.

The first step is warning. In the activity of this stage, a person is vitally negative eliminates another looming complication by eliminating the condition.

The second step is to solve the problem directly. This is a clear problem cognitive and behavioral power is used in solving.

The third stage - a person takes a critical approach to the results of the event. This The goal of the stage is to reduce the number of hits it takes and return to its previous normal state return sooner. This is the recovery phase.

In addition to comments, coping behavior is an individual's stress shows a relatively specific reaction. This means that when

When a person feels stress, he can cope cognitively and behaviorally in a problematic situation tries to do. This approach is based on the subject's daily and previous behavior taking into account its aspects, taking into account its aspects in overcoming the usual negative aspects can't. For example, this approach is one of the possibilities of an individual to avoid stress is an exception. Also, according to this requirement, a person reacts with stress life problem cannot be seen as overcome until it is entered.

The concept of "coping strategy" is also the management of process resources is widely analyzed. Eliminating life complications as expected essentially, it is done by mobilizing individual resources.

When coping strategies and their methods are distinguished from defense mechanisms. Constructive active necessity is implied and unpleasantness through the situation is an attempt to avoid. In psychology, there is a subject of coping, and it is special emotional mechanism and rational regulation in the research area learning life situations according to his target optimal behavior implements reconstruction according to its goals.

A person's coping behavior in stressful situations is stressful to a certain extent is important for the response in situations. Especially teenagers during this period, it is necessary to take a serious look at this process.

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